

COMPARISON STUDY ON DIGITAL AND TRADITIONAL MARKET

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Abstract:

Now a days the traditional users less than to compare digital market users, the reason the customers wants more collection of products and they have no time to buy the products in traditional market. So they choose an option to move the digital market, and customers to buy anything in this world just a one click and to get immediate, most of them choosing a digital market, and also they are to buy a product in traditional market.

Key Words: Digital Market, Traditional Market, Shopping

Introduction:

This study about the what are the reason to buy the products in traditional and digital market, While making any purchase decision consumer should know the medium to purchase whether digital market or the traditional market. Consumer should decide the channel for them which can best suit to their need and wants and which can satisfy them. In this competitive world how, consumer can decide the particular medium for their purchase of goods is very important to understand in a managerial point of view. Said that the internet shopping is the third best and most popular activity over internet after digital market next comes the e-mail using, instant messaging and web browsing. These are even more important than watching or getting entertain by the internet or getting any information or news, this are the two very common thought which comes to the people's mind when considering the internet users do when they are online. And this study about traditional market Vs digital market and what are the reasons customers to choose the traditional and digital markets.

Statement of the Problem:

Digital and traditional market users why they want to buy a products in traditional and digital market and now a days most of them to move the digital market some other customers they want to buy a products in both traditional and digital markets and the customers are satisfied or not, what are the products buy in digital and traditional market.

Objectives of the Study:

To investigate, which reason affects traditional and digital shopping?

Scope of Study:

The study analyze if there is any association between the literacy of the consumers and the type of markets they choose.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

The Primary data would be collected keeping in view the research objectives. Structured questionnaires have been collected from the respondents of public. The study involves collection of primary data through structured questionnaire from public and analysis of the data done with descriptive application of various statistical tools.

Method of Data Collection:

Primary data were collected by using well-structured questionnaires prepared by the researcher. It was sample collected. Overview the magazines and journals for updated articles which will help to arrive review of the literature

Sample Size:

Random of Data collected from out of 71 respondents, the data are to collected to variable methods, questionnaires, interview methods to collect the data about the study of traditional and digital market. The size of sample is 71 respondents.

Tools of Data Collection:

Simple Percentage Method:

Review of Literature:

The review of study is traditional market and digital market and its compare Traditional marketing refers to any type of marketing that isn't online. This means print, broadcast, direct mail, phone, and outdoor advertising like billboards. From newspapers to radio, this method of marketing helps reach targeted audiences. Image source: Ads of the World .The term digital marketing refers to the use of digital channels to market products and services in order to reach consumers. This type of marketing involves the use of websites, mobile

devices, social media, search engines, and other similar channels. And they choose the digital and traditional market both. That is a conclusion of this study. And this is evidence of from the study, and the consumers why they choose the traditional and digital market.

Simple Percentage and Interpretation:

Age:

S.No	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	18-20	3	4%
2	20-30	36	51%
3	30-40	19	27%
4	40-Above	13	18%
		71	100%

The above table shows the percentage of different age group of people. From 71 samples, (18-20) 3 respondents of 4%, belong the age group (20-30) 36 respondents of 51% and the age group belongs to (30-40) 19 respondents of 27% and above 40 age of people 18% out of 71 random samples.

Gender:

S.No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	49	69%
2	Female	31	31%
		71	100%

The above table shows the gender of the respondents, total number of respondents 71 and 49 respondents in 69% of male and 31 respondents 31% of female

Products Buy in Traditional Market:

S.No	Products	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Easy available products	5	21%
2	Costly and branded	-	-
3	Grocery items	2	8%
4	medicine	-	-
5	accessories	-	-
6	All of the above	17	71%
		24	100%

This table shows the study of what type of products brought in traditional market totally 24 respondents in the study, 5 number of respondents to choose easy available products in traditional market 21%, 2 number of respondents 8% to choose the grocery items, and 71% of the respondents to choose the all of the above (easy available products, costly and branded, medicine, accessories) 17 respondents to choose out of 24.

Products Buy in Digital Market:

S.No	Products	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Clothing, Cosmetics and Accessories & Footwear	12	55%
2	Medicine	3	13%
3	Electronics	4	18%
4	Others	3	14%
		22	100%

This table shows about the study of what type of products brought in digital market 12 respondents to choose the clothing, cosmetics, footwear and accessories in digital market 55% out of 22 respondents and this is majority of respondents to choose, 3 respondents to choose the medicine in digital market 13%, 4 respondents to choose the electronics items 18% of respondents, and 14% of respondents to choose the others in digital market.

Any Difficulties in Digital Market:

S.No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	13	59%
2	No	9	41%
		22	100%

This table shows about the study of respondents face the problems in digital market, 59% of respondents to choose the yes 9 respondents out of 22, and this is majority of respondents to responded, and 41% of respondents to choose the no option in digital market.

Any Difficulties in Traditional Market:

S.No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	7	29%
2	No	17	71%
		24	100%

This table shows the study about the difficulties in traditional market out of 24 respondents, 29% of respondents to choose the yes 7 respondents out of 24, and 71% respondents to choose the no option of the difficulties in traditional market 17 respondents out of 24 responded and this is majority of the responded.

Satisfaction Level in Traditional Market:

S.No	Rating	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Good	11	46%
2	Excellent	13	54%
3	Not Good	-	-
4	Poor	-	-
			100%

The above table shows the percentage of satisfied level of respondents in traditional market 46% respondents to choose the good rating out of 100%, balance 54% percentage of respondents to choose the excellent level of rating.

Satisfaction Level in Digital Market:

S.No	Rating	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Fully Satisfied	6	27%
2	Satisfied	13	59%
3	Dis Satisfied	3	14%
		22	100%

This table shows the percentage of satisfied respondents in digital market 27% of respondents fully satisfied, 59% Of respondents to choose the satisfied of digital market, and 14% respondents to dissatisfied in digital market.

Findings:

- Most of the respondents felt home delivery, offers, discounts and no issue of going out are very important in digital market.
- Most of the respondents felt check product quality, reliability in quality, easy return policies, different products, offers and discounts are important in traditional market.
- Some of the respondents are not doing digital market due to duplicate quality, risk in credit card and debit card payments, risk of theft, trouble with hidden cost.
- Various factors like safety, convenience, easy to return, quality check etc will influence the customer behavior and also in preferring the suitable shopping channel.

Suggestions:

- The respondents facing the delay in delivery problem so the problem has to resolve to improve the sales of digital market.
- Respondents facing transaction problems so the online websites has to solve the issue to improve the sales of digital market.
- So digital market has to provide good quality products so that more customers will buy the products in digital market
- 52% of respondents facing the problem damage of product frequently so the digital retail companies has to solve the problem.
- Issue in return policy is the problem faced by 30% respondents frequently so the digital retail companies have to fasten the process of returning the product

Conclusion:

In the modern era the growth and development of digital is unavoidable, but is the fact that majority of the rural people are not trusted these digital system, it is popular among the city people. It is the needed of an hour to mix the digital market with our traditional market and provide all facilities to the customers as they wanted.

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